

POSSIBILITIES OF WEB-QUEST TECHNOLOGY IN INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF TEACHING IMMUNOLOGY

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Annotation. This article provides feedback on the potential of webquest technology to enhance the effectiveness of immunology teaching.

Key words: web quest, global network, information and learning environment, virtual training ground, creativity, logical, creative.

The science of immunology deals with the study of homeostasis in the human body, a complex, multicomponent immune system that protects against destructive exogenous and endogenous factors, the mechanism of resistance to infectious diseases, the role of cellular and humoral factors in the development of immunity, the molecular structure of antibodies, their biosynthesis, lymphocytes and macrophages [1].

One of the problems of modern biological education is the complete communication of these topics to the consciousness of students [2]. Therefore, modern didactic e-learning in the teaching of immunology requires the active implementation of web quest resources and technologies through interaction and integration. A web quest is a solution to a problematic educational task with elements of role-playing games through information and educational environments in the global network, virtual learning platforms and Google search engines. The main idea of the web quest technology is to study the science of immunology using the global network. In this regard, according to E.N. Shalimova, I.L. Davydova, L.I. Gasheva, a web quest technology is being developed that allows integrating the Internet into the educational process in various disciplines as much as possible. They cover a specific problem, subject, topic.

A distinctive feature of web quests is that participants use various information and educational environments of the global network, virtual learning platforms and learning resources posted on websites to solve the problem independently or in groups [3, 4]. That is, to solve the problem of education with the help of the global network.

The use of web quest technology in the educational process allows to implement a system-activity approach to learning, as well as to form students' competencies in the field of information and communication technologies.

Regular use of quest technologies in the learning process develops personal, cognitive, communicative, and regulatory abilities of students [3, 4].

In this regard, according to N.B. Bondarenko, I.L. Davydova, L.I. Gasheva, the web quest technology is aimed at solving the problem of using global food and has the following advantages:

- allows the teacher to build lessons in a playful way, based on the creation of problem situations [3];
- develops students' culture of using the global network and develops analytical thinking skills and competence in using network materials of various levels of complexity [5];
- develops students' creative abilities and creative thinking;
- develops students' ability to think and make decisions independently [3];
- increases students' motivation, creativity, develops creative thinking and competence based on the creation of various problematic tasks on the topic [5];
- forms a culture of independent search for students on the project;
- develops in students the competence of independent learning [3].

Thus, the use of web quest technology in immunology sessions is effective, given the above possibilities. Classes on this technology contribute to the development of students' creative abilities in the field of immunology, develop logical and creative thinking.

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